

Sonic Cultures (2020)

SE-LIEN CHUANG, Atelier Avant, Austria

ANDREAS WEIXLER, MDW Vienna, ABPU Linz, Atelier Avant, Austria

1 PROGRAM NOTES

Sonic Cultures is an immersive realtime audiovisual compositional environment with interactive generative score (iScore) for multiple computer and open ensemble. An open acoustic instruments ensemble including electronic devices using digital interfaces (laptops etc.) serves as mutual media for score conducting, reading and interpreting. In concert it is performed within an combination of audiovisual realtime processing and improvisation conducted by interactive graphic scores on individual screens/computer driven by virtuoso random functions and intentional choices of a digital conductor/composer, which underline the visual and graphic components that are linked to and experienced by the musical sound environments. The conducted improvisation is completed by an audio realtime signal processing by fft controlled freeze reverb, classic ring modulation as well as spectral delay by a computer performer in mutual inducement with the instrumental player.

Fig. 1. screenshots of the related performance by Se-Lien Chuang & Andreas Weixler

2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Sonic Cultures (2020)

by Se-Lien Chuang & Andreas Weixler

Audiovisual realtime composition for open ensemble, iScore & live electronic originally planned premiere live at NIME20 Birmingham with local musicians Sonic Cultures is an immersive realtime audiovisual compositional environment with interactive generative score (iScore) for multiple computer and open ensemble. An open acoustic instruments

Licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). Copyright remains with the author(s).

ensemble including electronic devices using digital interfaces (laptops etc.) serves as mutual media for score conducting, reading and interpreting. In concert it is performed within an combination of audiovisual realtime processing and improvisation conducted by interactive graphic scores on individual screens/computer driven by virtuoso random functions and intentional choices of a digital conductor/composer, which underline the visual and graphic components that are linked to and experienced by the musical sound environments. The conducted improvisation is completed by an audio realtime signal processing by fft controlled freeze reverb, classic ring modulation as well as spectral delay by a computer performer in mutual inducement with the instrumental player.

The essence of this compositional environment is to entice and to express the musical ideas by offering the visual and graphic incentive within the personal and individual spontaneity of the performer and the composer. Further it aims to crosslink the aural and visual environments for the performer and especially for the audience by fulfilling the audiovisual realtime processing through the multichannel audio processing and sound spatialization on the one hand, on the other hand the large-size projection of the visual transformation. An interactive score turns the concert into live-event of a very special kind: the score is assembled within an algorithmic/random realtime process on stage based on mainly graphic notation.

iScore - by the wave of a hand interactive score

Fig. 2. screenshots of the related performance by Se-Lien Chuang & Andreas Weixler

performer and composer process an interactive score and exert mutual influence on it:

- chooses page of a graphic score (including traditional notes)
- by the wave of a hand (gesture of turning page)
- Each computer can act independently but also as a swarm

Sonic Cultures (2020)

- each computer can send actual & favorite score-page

one or more conductor/composer

3 PERFORMANCE NOTES

The essence of this compositional environment is to entice and to express the musical ideas by offering the visual and graphic incentive within the personal and individual spontaneity of the performer and the composer. Further it aims to crosslink the aural and visual environments for the performer and especially for the audience by fulfilling the audiovisual realtime processing through the multichannel audio processing and sound spatialization on the one hand, on the other hand the large-size projection of the visual transformation. An interactive score turns the concert into live-event of a very special kind: the score is assembled within an algorithmic/random realtime process on stage based on mainly graphic notation.

4 MEDIA LINKS

- Video: <https://youtu.be/T1700ByTaVU>

This video shows the concert of the related conceived piece „Momentum ACCAD“ premier on the 23rd September 2019, with the Sonic Arts Ensemble at The Motion Lab, ACCAD OSU - Advanced Computing Center for the Arts and Design at The Ohio State University in Columbus in the framework of „Virtuoso Chances“ - Portrait Se-Lien Chuang & Andreas Weixler.

Credits:

The OSU Sonic Arts Ensemble (Marc Ainger and Federico Camara Halac, co- directors)

Jacob Kopcienski - saxophone

Samantha Burgess - violin

Yildiz Guventurk - percussion

Federico Camara Halac - thornblower

Se-Lien Chuang - realtime video processing

Andreas Weixler - realtime audio processing & iScore conducting